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Pultrusion of Glass Fibre Reinforced / Maleated-PP modified / PP Matrix Composites

Wendy K. Y. Poon, Y. Z. Jin and Robert K. Y. Li

*Department of Physics and Materials Science
City University of Hong Kong,
Tat Chee Avenue, Kowloon, Hong Kong*

ABSTRACT: An initially designed pultruder for the pultrusion of thermoset matrix composites was modified for thermoplastic pultrusion. Components such as creel stand, guidance devices, preheater, pultrusion die and cooling die were either modified or introduced. This paper describes the pultruder modification as well as reporting on the pultrusion of glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GFRPP) composites. Flexural properties of the pultruded GFRPP under quasi-static and impact rates of loading were also reported. The weak GF/PP interface was modified by adding different percentages of maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene (MA-g-PP). The addition of the MA-g-PP results in a significant increase in the flexural performance. Different failure phenomena were also addressed.

KEYWORDS: Maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene, Thermoplastic pultrusion, Flexural strength, Buckling

INTRODUCTION

The pultrusion of thermosetting matrix composites is a well developed process [1]. However, the change over to the pultrusion of thermoplastic matrix composites is not straightforward due to the differences in the consolidation behaviour and the flow characteristics between the two types of polymer resins. In the pultrusion of thermosetting matrix composites, the resin is in general either unsaturated polyester, epoxy, or poly(vinyl ester). Before entering the pultrusion die, they remain as a liquid with relatively low viscosity. Therefore, wetting between the fibre and matrix is easy.

For thermoplastic matrix pultrusion, a number of techniques have been employed to provide the needed close contact between the fibre and matrix before they enter the heated forming die. They are: prepreg tapes [2-6], powder-impregnated or powder-impregnated sheathed yarn [7-11], and commingled hybrid tow [12, 13]. The pre-processed materials, whether it is prepreg tape, powder-impregnated yarn, or commingled hybrid tow will be fed directly into the heated pultrusion die (with a pre-heating zone in most cases) for melting and subsequent consolidation. In these studies, the matrix systems studied include polyetheretherketone (PEEK) [2, 3, 5], polypropylene (PP) [2, 4, 6, 12], polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) [3, 8], nylon [13], polyetherketoneketone (PEKK) [7], and polybutylene-terephthalate (PBT) [9].

The pultrusion of glass fibre reinforced PP through the prepreg tapes and commingled hybrid tow routes have been compared in an earlier study by Holland and Tomlinson [14]. With the same fibre content ($V_f = 51\%$), it was reported that the flexural modulus and flexural strength for the pultruded GFRPP produced through the prepreg tapes route were significantly higher than that produced through the commingled hybrid tow route. However, the shear strengths for the pultruded GFRPP produced using the prepreg tapes were significantly lower. These observations were explained and correlated with the observation that for the commingled hybrid tow prepared pultruded GFRPP, misalignment of the glass fibres occurred.

The prepreg tapes route will be employed in this project for the production of GFRPP for the

subsequent pultrusion. The technology of thermoplastic prepreg tape production can also be applied to other thermoplastic composite manufacturing methods, such as compression moulding, tape winding, and long fibre injection moulding. Peltonen et al [15] have carried out a parametric study on the production of glass fibre/PP prepregs. The degree of impregnation was found to improve with the use of coupling agents such as maleic anhydride modified PP. Maleic anhydride modified PP has been found to be an effective coupling agent to induce better bonding between PP and glass fibre [16].

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Pultrusion Machine

A small pultrusion machine (Harbin FRP Institute, Model: HB/LJ-3), originally designed for thermoset pultrusion, has been modified in this project for thermoplastic pultrusion. The facilities used for thermosets and thermoplastics pultrusion may look similar at a first glance, but there are significant and subtle differences that one has to pay special attention to. These modifications include prepreg production, introduction of pre-heating and cooling dies, as well as the modification of the actual pultrusion die. They will be presented in the following sections.

Prepreg Tape Preparation

In order to overcome the problem of high melt viscosity of most thermoplastic matrices and to achieve a thorough impregnation of the fibre tows by the matrix, prepreg tapes were first prepared. Bundles of glass fibres were pulled through a specially designed die attached to a Brabender twin screw compounder. In the twin screw compounder, PP and MA-g-PP pre-mixed in the required ratios were melt blended. In this study, PP/MA-g-PP in the weight ratios of 100/0, 97.5/2.5, and 95/5 were used as the matrices for pultrusion. In order to prevent oxidation of the PP, stabilizer was also added. The melt-blended PP after coming out from the die exit deposited onto the glass fibre tows. The matrix impregnation into the glass fibres bundles was facilitated by passing through sets of rollers. The torque and tension exerted on the fibre tows can be adjusted to achieve for better impregnation. The prepreg tapes were then cooled by air at ambient temperature and finally all prepreg tapes were wound onto individual bobbins for later pultrusion. Prepreg tapes with cross section area approximately equals to 12×2 mm were prepared.

Pultrusion of GF/PP Prepreg Tapes

The major difference between thermoset and thermoplastic pultrusion is the die design. In thermoset pultrusion, a single die is used for the curing of the thermoset matrix. For thermoplastic pultrusion, a number of dies: pre-heating die, main pultrusion die, and cooling die are needed. The vertical and horizontal position of the prepreg tapes were controlled by passing through two sets of individual guidance devices (Fig. 1) before entering the pre-heating die. The pre-heating die (160-170 °C) heated up the prepreg tapes so as to soften the PP matrix. Subsequently, the pre-heated prepreg tapes entered the main pultrusion die (260 °C) where complete melting of the PP melt took place. The high pressure inside the main pultrusion die forced the PP melt to impregnate the glass fibre tows completely. As the pultruded composite profile came out from the main pultrusion die, it was cooled by passing through the cooling die, which temperature was controlled by the flow of water. In this experiment, the temperature of the cooling die was at 70-80 °C. The pulling speed that can be achieved was 30 cm/min.

Materials

Polypropylene (PP) homopolymer (Pro-fax 6331, Montell) was used as the matrix for pultrusion. In order to improve the fibre/matrix interfacial bonding, small percentages of a maleic-anhydride grafted polypropylene (MA-g-PP) (Epolene G-3003, Eastman) were pre-blended with the PP. Continuous E-glass fibres with diameter about 10-15 µm were used as the reinforcement.

The pultruded GFRPP specimens with the PP/MA-g-PP weight ratios of 100/0, 97.5/2.5, and 95/5 will be designated as MA-0, MA-2.5 and MA-5 respectively.

Fibre Weight Fraction

The fibre weight fraction was determined by burning off the PP matrix of the pultruded GFRPP at 600 °C inside an air-circulating furnace. The residue glass fibres were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath and weighted using an electronic balance. The fibre weight fraction is therefore obtained from:

$$W_f = \frac{\text{weight of glass fibre}}{\text{weight of composite}} \quad (1)$$

Five measurements were made and the average values as well as the standard deviations were reported.

Flexural Test

Three-point-bending flexural tests were carried out at quasi-static and impact rates of loadings. The quasi-static rate tests were conducted using an Instron testing machine (model 4206), and the results measured at loading rates of 0.1 and 10mm/min will be reported in this paper. Impact tests were conducted using a Fractovis instrumented drop weight impact tester (Ceast, Italy) at 3 m/s. Dimensions of the samples were 80 × 14.7 × 2.9 mm, with span and span/depth ratio of 64 mm and 22 respectively. At each condition, seven samples were tested. The flexural strength S , and flexural modulus (E_B) were calculated from the following two equations:

$$S = \frac{3 P L}{2 b d^2} \quad (2)$$

$$E_B = \frac{L^3 m}{4 b d^3} \quad (3)$$

where P is the peak load; L , b and d are the specimen span, width, and depth respectively. m is the initial slope of the load-deflection curve. All tests were carried out at room temperature.

Microscopy examination

Voids in the pultruded GRFPP composites were examined by optical microscopy after cold mounting in epoxy resin, and followed by grinding and polishing. Some tested specimens were examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Jeol JSM-820) with gold coating (Jeol JFC-1100E) prior to examination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fibre weight fractions (W_f) for the pultruded composites are listed in Table 1, and it is obvious that both MA-0 and MA-2.5 have similar fibre contents. The W_f for MA-5 was about 5% higher than the other two systems. During pultrusion, it was found that some glass fibres were trapped inside but close to the die-entrance of the main pultrusion die. Therefore, as both MA-0 and MA-2.5 have similar glass fibre content, a comparison between the two systems is indicative of the effects of PP maleation.

Table 1 Fibre weight fraction of the pultruded GFRPP composites

Pultruded GFRPP composites	W_f (%) (Standard deviation)
MA-0	65.92 (0.58)
MA-2.5	65.71 (1.16)
MA-5	71.23 (0.37)

Fig. 2 shows typical force-displacement curves for the three types of composites measured in the three-point-bending flexural tests at 10 mm/min. All three composites showed an initial linear elastic region up to near the maximum load, although some slight non-linearity can be identified just before reaching the maximum load. This was followed by a load-drop, with the maleated PP systems (i.e. MA-2.5 and MA-5) showed more rapid load-drops, and more gentle for the MA-0 composite. The more rapid load-drops for the maleated PP composites are probably related to the stronger interfacial bonding. The maximum load was higher in the maleated systems, and will be used in the calculation of the flexural strength by using eqn. 2. After the load-drop, the force remained constant with further bending of the specimens.

Similar behaviour was also observed for the impact flexural tests, and the force-time curves for the three composites are shown in Fig. 3.

From the force-displacement curves, and substituting the maximum force and slope of the initial force-displacement curves into eqns. 2 and 3 respectively, the flexural strength and flexural modulus were calculated and the results are shown in Fig. 4 and 5 respectively. In employing eqn. 2 to calculate the flexural strength, one assumes that the specimens failed in flexural mode, i.e. tensile cracks initiated at the lower surface of the flexural specimens. However, it was observed that the major damage mechanisms were related to compression failures above the neutral plane and the indentation damage on the top surface caused by the hard loading nose. The flexural strengths shown in Fig. 4 should therefore be called “*apparent flexural strength - S_A* ”. When comparing S_A for the MA-0 and MA-2.5 composites (both containing 66 wt% of glass fibres), it is obvious that maleation of the PP matrix gave definite improvements.

As for the flexural modulus (Fig. 5), the effect of matrix maleation is not as strong as that produced by the higher fibre content. The flexural modulus for the MA-5 composite, which contained 5 wt% more glass fibres (see Table 1), is definitely higher than that for the MA-0 and MA-2.5 composites.

Figs.6 and 7 show the top surfaces close to the loading line for specimens flexural tested at the low loading rate of 0.1 mm/min. For the MA-0 specimen, which contained no maleation, it can be seen that the fibre was not coated by PP matrix (Fig. 6). This indicates the weak interfacial bonding between glass fibre and PP. For the MA-2.5 specimen (Fig. 7), the glass fibre was strongly bonded to the PP matrix. These obviously show that the wetting was improved after adding MA-g-PP into the PP homopolymer.

As mentioned earlier, the measured apparent flexural strength S_A (Fig. 4), for the pultruded GRFPP composites was related to the indentation contact damage between the loading nose and the top surface of the specimens (Fig. 8). However, different failure patterns were identified between the non-maleated and maleated specimens. For the MA-0 (non-maleated) samples, the region below the loading nose was indented inward, and clear indentation lines can be observed (Fig. 8a). In contrary for the maleated specimens (MA-2.5 and MA-5), the region below the loading nose was raised upward (Figs. 8b and 8c). The set of specimens shown in Fig. 8 were tested at 3 m/s. Similar failure appearances were also observed under different loading rates and the damaged areas increased with loading rates.

In order to understand the failure mechanisms better, the failed specimens were sectioned with diamond saw and then polished for SEM examination. As can be seen from Figs. 9 and 10, significant fibre micro-buckling occurred into both non-maleated and maleated composites. These fibre micro-buckling were induced due to the compressive stress existed above the neutral plane under flexural loading. The locations for the fibre micro-buckling were differed in the non-maleated and maleated composites. For the non-maleated MA-0 specimens, two *buckling zones* were found to occur neighbouring to, but not directly under the loading line (Fig. 9). For the maleated specimens (MA-2.5 and MA-5), the *buckling zone* occurred directly underneath the loading line (Fig. 10). As the buckling zone could not develop towards the neutral plane, they were pointed upward towards the loading line, and gave rise to the raised regions under the loading nose as shown in Figs. 8b and 8c. The occurrences of the buckling zones are likely to be related to the GF/PP interfacial bond strength. Further works will definitely be needed in order to give meaningful explanation for the location of the *buckling zones* and the increased apparent flexural strength for the composites.

CONCLUSION

A small thermoset pultrusion machine was successfully modified for the pultrusion of glass fibre reinforced PP composites. Addition of MA-g-PP into the PP matrix improved the interfacial bonding between the matrix and fibres, and the flexural properties were also improved. The detailed failure mechanisms under flexural loading were also found to be different between the non-maleated and maleated composites.

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Fig. 1 Photographs showing the (a) horizontal and (b) vertical guidance devices.

Fig. 2 Flexural force-displacement curves measured at 10mm/min.

Fig. 3 Impact force-time curves measured at 3m/s.

Fig. 4 Apparent flexural strength against loading rate.

Fig. 5 Flexural modulus against loading rate.

Fig. 6 SEM photograph showing the top view of a MA-0 specimen tested at 0.1mm/min

Fig. 7 SEM photograph showing the top view of a MA-2.5 specimen tested at 0.1mm/min

Fig. 8 SEM photographs showing the damaged region below the loading nose. The specimens were tested at 3m/s. (a) MA-0; (b) MA-2.5; (c) MA-5.

Fig. 9 (a) Longitudinally sectioned view of an impacted tested MA-0 specimen. (b) Higher magnification showing the *buckling zone*.

Fig. 10 (a) Longitudinally sectioned view of an impacted tested MA-2.5 specimen. (b) Higher magnification showing the *buckling zone*.